

INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS on AGRICULTURE and ANIMAL SCIENCES

7-9 November 2018

Alanya / Turkey

Oral Presentation

The Effects Of Various Doses of Vermicompost Solid and Tea Applications on Total Phenolic Content and Some Phenological Parameters Of Sweet Basil (*Ocimum basilicum* L.).

İlker TÜRKAY¹, Lokman ÖZTÜRK², F. Şüheyda HEPŞEN TÜRKAY¹

¹ Kırşehir Ahi Evran University, Agricultural Faculty, Department of Soil Sciences and Plant Nutrition, Kırşehir/Turkey

² Tokat Gaziosmanpaşa University, Faculty of Arts and Sciences, Department of Biology, Tokat/Turkey

*Corresponding Author E-mail: ilker.turkay@ahievran.edu.tr

Abstract

Organic fertilizer application on basil cultivation is highly recommended to preserve its natural aroma and essential oil yield. In this study, 7 doses (0%, 4%, 8%, 12%, 16%, 20%, and 24%) of vermicomposts applied through two different application methods; solid vermicompost (SV) to the root zone and vermicompost tea (VT) as foliar spray. At the end of the 10th week of the vegetational development, some phenological characters including fresh weight, dry weight, plant height and leaf length were recorded and leaves at similar positions of each individual were harvested and then subjected to total phenolic content analysis. According to the results, the highest increase and amount of total phenolic content were determined at the application dose of 24% SV with the rate of 67%. Although, the SV applications increased total phenolic content at the doses of 4%, 8%, 12%, and 24% more than the same doses of VT; the VT application doses of 16% and 20% increased the total phenolic content more than the same doses of SV applications. Despite the highest total phenolic content increase was determined at the 24% SV application group as 67%, there was not a significant decrease in the phenological parameters of this application group when compared with the other SV application doses. Nevertheless, the highest values of phenological parameters and conversely a decrease as -34% in total phenolic content were determined at the highest VT application dose of 24%. The results obtained from the solid vermicompost applied groups revealed that the 24% SV application induced the total phenolic compound synthesis more than the other application doses without causing a significant decrease in the phenological parameters. Besides, the application of 24% vermicompost tea through foliar spraying decreased the total phenolic compound synthesis and conversely induced biomass production considerably, indicating an inverse relationship between them.

Keywords: Basil, Vermicompost, Total Phenolic Content, Organic Fertilizer.

INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS on AGRICULTURE and ANIMAL SCIENCES

7-9 November 2018

Alanya / Turkey

Introduction

Sweet basil (*Ocimum basilicum* L.) is a well-known medicinal and aromatic plant and commonly utilized for culinary and medicinal purposes around the world due to its rich phenolic and terpenoid compounds. Organic fertilizer application on basil cultivation is highly recommended to preserve its natural aroma and the essential oil yield (Hiltunen and Holm, 1999). Vermicompost products are utilized as organic fertilizer and du Jardin (2015) categorized them as biostimulants along with the other humic extracts.

Plant biostimulant products are novel in agronomy and more efficient in medicinal plants due to possibility of genetic manipulation in synthesis pathways of secondary metabolites (Raffie et al., 2016). It was reported that the application of plant biostimulants in various concentrations results in different effects by diverse mechanisms of action on medicinal plants (Raffie et al., 2016). The aim of this study was to reveal the effects of solid and aqueous forms of vermicompost applications on the total phenolic content and some phenological characters of sweet basil. Thus, a first comparison between two different application methods was carried out to evaluate their effectiveness on total phenolic content, which are produced through phenylpropanoid metabolization.

Material and Method

The seeds of plant material basil were acquired from a seed and farming equipments supplier in Kırşehir/TURKEY. Basil seeds were sown in 3 seeds per 50 cc containers in a greenhouse in October. At the 2nd week of the germination, one individual in each container selected and the others eliminated. The application groups were consisted of 10 basil individuals. Vermicompost solid applications were carried out by mixing vermicompost solids with soil for the rates of 0%, 4%, 8%, 12%, 16%, 20%, and 24% to brought final volume of 50 cc for each container.

Figure 1. Views of basils in the green house and plant growth room.

The 0%, 4%, 8%, 12%, 16%, 20%, and 24% concentrated vermicompost teas were prepared by shaking determined amount of vermicompost solid with distilled water over 4 hrs and filtering 4 times through a cheese cloth on the eve of every treatment in according to Edwards (2011). The teas applied to the groups once a week beginning from the 2nd week of germination until the harvest at the 10th week.

Fresh weight of every individual was recorded following plant height and the longest leaf length measurements at the harvest day. Upper leaves at similar positions of each individual of application groups were harvested as 15 g, dried at shadow and room temperature and then subjected to total phenolic content analysis. Total phenolic concentration in the extracts was determined spectrophotometrically according to the Folin-Ciocalteu method (Singleton et al. 1999). Foliar application of vermicompost teas were carried out avoiding from dripping of excess tea to soil and ensuring that the whole surface of leaves was wet.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed by ANOVA and means were separated by Duncan's Multiple-Range Test at $P < 0,05$. Statistical analysis was performed with SPSS statistic software package (1999).

Research Findings and Discussion

The measurements of phenological characters consisted of plant height, leaf length, fresh and dry weights varied among the application doses. SV applications to basil individuals positively affected all of the phenological parameters when compared to control.

Figure 2. The Effects of Increasing Doses of Solid Vermicompost Applications on Phenological Characters of Basil

The highest mean height was determined in the 4% solid vermicompost application group and the 8% and 20% application groups followed it, respectively. The longest leaf length mean value belonged to 12% SV application group, followed by groups of 4% and 24%, respectively. The highest value of fresh weight among solid vermicompost application groups belonged to the group of 12%, followed by groups of 4% and 20%, respectively. In terms of dry weight, 4%, 20% and 12% vermicompost application groups have the highest values, respectively.

Figure 3. The Effects of Increasing Doses of Vermicompost Tea Applications on Phenological Characters of Basil

As a result of the application of vermicompost teas to the leaves as a foliar spray, which were prepared from the solid vermicompost; the highest length, leaf length, fresh weight and dry weight values were observed in 24% liquid vermicompost treatment group. A remarkable result was observed in the dry weight mean value of 24% vermicompost tea application group, revealing an increase as 44% and 144% when compared with the previous dose of vermicompost tea application and control groups, respectively.

Figure 4. The Effects of Increasing Doses of Vermicompost Solid and Tea Applications on Dry Weight of Basil

Fig. 4 shows that 24% vermicompost tea application group was characterized by a significant increase in dry weight, which represents biomass, when compared with the other vermicompost solid and tea application doses. It was seen that the increase in dry weight was in direct proportion to the increasing doses of vermicompost tea applications.

Figure 5. The effects of vermicompost solid and tea applications on total phenolic content of basil

Figure 12 shows that the effects of vermicompost application in solid or liquid form on total phenolic content vary according to the type and dose of application. Among the application doses of solid vermicompost, the highest total phenolic content was determined in the 24% SV application group. Following this group, the highest value was determined in the 8% SV application group. The highest amounts of total phenolic content among the vermicompost tea application groups were determined in 20% VT, 8% VT and 16% VT groups when compared to the control group, respectively. The lowest total phenolic content was determined in 24% VT application group in contrast to total phenolic content amount of same dose of solid vermicompost application. Although, a significant decrease was determined in 12% VT application group compared to 8% VT application group, the lowest total phenolic content decrease, even though lower than 8% VT and control group, was determined in 24% VT application group.

Results and Suggestions

In addition to the presence of humic acid in the content of vermicompost, which is classified as a plant biostimulant (du Jardin, 2015), the existence of auxin and cytokine and their related compounds are also known to have positive effects on plant growth and development (Scaglia et al., 2016). In this study, different application methods and vermicompost applications those performed at different doses were determined to be effective on some phenological

INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS on AGRICULTURE and ANIMAL SCIENCES

7-9 November 2018

Alanya / Turkey

characteristics such as plant height and leaf length, dry and fresh weight, as well as total phenolic content of sweet basil. The most effective doses among the solid vermicompost (SV) applications were 4%, 12% and 20% application doses in terms of plant height and leaf length, respectively, with close mean values. The effects of vermicompost tea (liquid vermicompost) application with different concentrations through spraying to the leaves of the basil individuals were determined in a tendency to increase in direct proportion to the increasing doses and the application dose of 24% was determined as the most effective dose in this respect.

Among the SV application groups, the highest values in terms of biomass gain are observed between 4%, 20% and 12% groups and close values respectively. Vermicompost tea spraying to basil leaves revealed a tendency to increase in proportion to the increasing concentrations in terms of dry weight. In the 24% VT group with the highest dose of vermicompost, dry weight rate was found to be increased by 144% compared to the control group and by a 44% increase compared to the previous application dose of 20% VT. It was determined that the ratio of the dry weight to the fresh weight of 24% VT group (% 16,76) was higher by 93% than the dry/fresh weight ratio (% 8,64) of 4% SV application group which was the highest ratio among the other solid vermicompost application groups. This notable difference between the effects of vermicompost applications to the plant root zone or foliar spraying on the leaves indicates that the application of high doses of liquid vermicompost is more successful in biomass production, and thus the bioavailability of the vermicompost tea application is higher. However, in comparison with all other groups, the plant height mean value of the 4% SV group was the highest, while the 24% VT group has a higher dry weight value despite it has relatively lower height mean value compared to 4% SV group. Similarly, the leaf length mean value of 4% SV group was 7% greater than 24% VT group. As a result of these comparisons, it was observed that the vermicompost tea application significantly increased biomass by increasing body and leaf thickness rather than increasing plant height and leaf length. In addition, it was seen that the SV groups were predominant in VT groups in terms of average height and leaf length. The effects of auxin, cytokine and related compounds on plant height and leaf length in the composition of vermicompost have been observed to be more efficient with vermicompost applied from soil.

Total phenolic contents of vermicompost application groups were determined to vary according to the application method. SV application groups revealed an increase by 53% till 8% SV application group and a decrease till 20% SV application group in terms of total phenolic content. However, it was seen that the highest total phenolic content was determined in the 24% SV group. Considering the phenological parameters, there was no regression in this application group compared to the control group. Therefore, vermicompost which was applied at high dose to the plant root zone was found to increase the synthesis of phenolic compounds which are important defense compounds of basil individuals without causing a decrease in plant growth and development.

The highest total phenolic compounds among the VT groups were found in 8% VT and 20% VT application groups, respectively, and the lowest total phenolic content determined in 24% VT application group. Thus, the total phenolic content in the group treated with high concentrated (24% VT) vermicompost tea by spraying was lower than the control group, and

INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS on AGRICULTURE and ANIMAL SCIENCES

7-9 November 2018

Alanya / Turkey

the biomass production in this group increased considerably, the application of vermicompost in the form of foliar spray appears to induce the basil individuals to increase the primary metabolic activities instead of the synthesis of secondary metabolites. However, it is possible that the vermicompost tea application at a concentration of more than 20% may have a negative effect on the total phenolic compound synthesis in basil.

Acknowledgment:

We thank to Dr. Didem SAĞLAM for data analyses and allocating plant growth room to grow basil for this study.

References

- du Jardin, P., 2015. Plant biostimulants: Definition, concept, main categories and regulation. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 196, 3-14. doi:10.1016/j.scienta.2015.09.021
- Edwards, C.A., Arancon, N., Sherman, R., 2011. *Vermiculture thecnology, Earthworms, Organic Wastes, and Environmental Management*. CRC Press Taylor & Francis Group. 578 p.
- R. Hiltunen and Y. Holm (Eds.), 1999. *Basil. The genus Ocimum*, Harwood Academic Publishers, 182 pp., ISBN 90-5702-432-2, Amsterdam.
- Rafiee, H., Naghdi Badi, H., Mehrafarin, A., Qaderi, A., Zarinpanjeh, N., Sekara, A., & Zand, E., 2016. Application of plant biostimulants as new approach to improve the biological responses of medicinal plants- A critical review, *Journal of Medicinal Plants*, 3(59), 6-39.
- Scaglia, B., Nunes, R. R., Rezende, M. O. O., Tambone, F., & Adani, F., 2016. Investigating organic molecules responsible of auxin-like activity of humic acid fraction extracted from vermicompost, *Sci Total Environ*, 562, 289-295. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.03.212
- Singleton, V.L., Orthofer, R., Lamuela-Raventos, R.M., 1999. Analysis of total phenols and other oxidation substrates and antioxidants by means of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. *Methods in Enzymology*. 299: 152-178. doi: 10.1016/S0076-6879(99)99017-1
- SPSS. 1999. *SPSS for Windows, Release 10.0.1*. SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA.